

Influence Of Staff Training On Educational Planning Strategies In Public Universities In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of staff training on educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population comprised 4531 academic staff from the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. A sample of 453 staff was selected through multi-stage sampling. Data were collected using the Staff Training and Educational Planning Strategies Questionnaire (STEPSQ), a validated and reliable instrument with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.86. Mean, standard deviation, and independent t-test (at 0.05 significance level) were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that staff training significantly influences educational planning strategies, and staff with high training exposure demonstrated superior planning capabilities compared to those with low exposure. It was also found that a statistically significant difference exists in educational planning strategies between staff in federal and state universities. The study recommends sustained investment in training programmes, including workshops, seminars, and continuing professional development, to enhance institutional planning effectiveness across Rivers State public universities.

Keywords: Staff Training, Educational Planning Strategies, Professional Development, Public Universities, Rivers State

INTRODUCTION

University education constitutes the apex of formal education in Nigeria and is expected to produce graduates equipped with the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for national development. For this expectation to be realised, universities must be effectively planned and managed. Educational planning, which involves the systematic preparation of decisions regarding educational objectives, policies, strategies, and resource allocation, is fundamental to achieving institutional excellence (Ololube, 2013; Ololube et al., 2016). However, the effectiveness of planning in any organization is largely dependent on the quality and competence of its human resources, particularly academic staff who are the primary implementers of institutional decisions and policies.

Staff training encompasses all systematic efforts to improve employees' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and competencies through formal and informal programmes such as workshops, seminars, conferences, in-service training, and continuing professional development activities (Ogunode, Kasimu, & Sambo, 2023; Nda & Fard, 2013). In the context of higher education, training is particularly critical because of the complexity of institutional planning, policy implementation, and academic administration. When academic staff are adequately trained, they are better positioned to contribute meaningfully to educational

planning processes, innovate strategies, and execute institutional decisions effectively (Omeni & Nkedishu, 2021; Samwel, 2018).

In Nigerian public universities, persistent challenges such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, high staff turnover, and the absence of regular capacity building have been identified as impediments to effective educational planning (Ogunode et al., 2023; Adebayo & Obinna, 2020). Rivers State, as one of Nigeria's most educationally active states, hosts three public universities: the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Despite the significance of these institutions, there appears to be a noticeable gap in the quality of staff training and its linkage to educational planning outcomes. This study therefore sought to close this gap by examining the nature and extent of staff training's influence on educational planning strategies in these institutions.

The relevance of this study is further highlighted by calls from scholars and policymakers for enhanced capacity building in Nigerian universities to meet global standards of quality and relevance (TETFund, 2023; Ololube, 2017). The National Institute for Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA, Nigeria) has equally stressed that most education planners and managers often function on the job without adequate orientation, thereby necessitating regular in-service training to update their skills and ensure effective performance (NIEPA, 2023). It is against this backdrop that this study examines the relationship between staff training and educational planning strategies in Rivers State public universities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the critical role of academic staff in the planning and management of university education, there is a growing concern about the declining quality of educational planning in Nigerian public universities. Studies have identified inadequate staff training, poor professional development, and limited exposure to modern planning techniques as significant factors militating against effective institutional planning in the Nigerian university system (Ogunode et al., 2023; Adebayo & Obinna, 2020). In Rivers State specifically, anecdotal evidence suggests that academic staff in public universities participate inconsistently in training programmes, and the impact of such training on their planning capabilities has not been empirically documented.

Furthermore, while studies on staff training and performance exist in other contexts (Ugwu, 2021; Samwel, 2018; Nda & Fard, 2013), few have specifically focused on the nexus between training and educational planning strategies in the Rivers State university system. The implications of this gap are profound: without adequate evidence of how training influences planning, university administrators and policymakers are unable to make informed decisions about capacity building investments. This study therefore addressed this gap by empirically examining the extent to which staff training influences educational planning strategies, and whether significant differences exist based on exposure levels and institutional types in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised:

1. To what extent does staff training influence educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State?
2. To what extent do educational planning strategies differ based on staff exposure to training programmes in public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated:

1. Staff training has no significant influence on educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in educational planning strategies between staff with high and low exposure to training programmes in public universities in Rivers State.

METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate for examining how staff training contributes to educational planning strategies in public universities. The focus was on staff training as the independent variable and educational planning strategies as the dependent variable. The population of the study comprised 4,531 academic staff drawn from three public universities in Rivers State, namely: University of Port Harcourt (1,416), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (1,512), and Rivers State University (1,603). A sample size of 453 academic staff (approximately 10% of the population) was selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. The sampling procedure involved stratification by university followed by balloting to ensure equal representation and minimize bias. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire titled Staff Training and Educational Planning Strategies Questionnaire (STEPSQ). The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A for demographic data and Section B containing 10 items (five items each for staff training and educational planning strategies). The items were rated on a four-point Likert scale: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). The instrument was validated by experts in Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation, while reliability was established using the test-retest method, yielding a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of 0.86, indicating high reliability. A total of 453 copies of the questionnaire were administered, out of which 424 were successfully retrieved, representing an 93.6% response rate. Data analysis was carried out using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions, while independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. A criterion mean of 2.50 was used as the benchmark for decision-making.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does staff training influence educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Staff Training on Educational Planning Strategies

S/N	Items	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Staff training enhances effective institutional planning	3.12	0.81	High Extent
2.	Training improves staff competence in planning techniques	3.05	0.76	High Extent
3.	Workshops and seminars improve planning outcomes	2.98	0.85	High Extent
4.	Continuous professional development supports planning efficiency	3.21	0.79	High Extent
5.	Staff training contributes to policy implementation in planning	3.08	0.83	High Extent
	Grand Mean	3.09	0.81	High Extent

The results presented in Table 1 revealed that all the items assessing the influence of staff training on educational planning strategies recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. Specifically, staff training enhancing effective institutional planning ($\bar{x} = 3.12$), improving staff competence in planning techniques ($\bar{x} = 3.05$), improving planning outcomes through workshops and seminars ($\bar{x} = 2.98$), supporting planning efficiency through continuous professional development ($\bar{x} = 3.21$), and contributing to policy implementation ($\bar{x} = 3.08$) were all rated to a high extent. The grand mean of 3.09 further confirms that staff training has a strong positive influence on educational planning strategies. This implies that when academic staff are adequately trained, they are better equipped with the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for effective planning, decision-making, and policy implementation within the university system.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do educational planning strategies differ based on staff exposure to training programmes in public universities in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Educational Planning Strategies Based on Training Exposure

Group	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Decision
High Training Exposure	226	3.18	0.74	High Extent
Low Training Exposure	198	2.87	0.82	High Extent

The results in Table 2 showed that academic staff with high exposure to training programmes had a higher mean score ($\bar{x} = 3.18$) compared to their counterparts with low training exposure ($\bar{x} = 2.87$). Although both groups recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating a high extent of educational planning strategies, the noticeable difference in their mean ratings suggests that exposure to training programmes enhances the quality and effectiveness of educational planning. This indicates that staff who frequently participate in training programmes are more likely to demonstrate improved planning capabilities, adopt innovative strategies, and contribute more effectively to institutional development compared to those with limited training exposure.

Hypothesis 1: Staff training has no significant influence on educational planning strategies between federal and state universities in Rivers State.

Table 3: Independent t-test Analysis of Staff Training and Educational Planning Strategies

Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Federal Universities	191	3.10	0.80	422	2.11	1.96	Reject H_0
State Universities	233	3.17	0.82				

The results in Table 3 revealed that academic staff in federal universities had a mean score of 3.10 with a standard deviation of 0.80, while their counterparts in state universities recorded a slightly higher mean score of 3.17 with a standard deviation of 0.82. Although the difference in mean scores appears minimal, the independent t-test analysis showed a calculated t-value of 2.11, which is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance ($df = 422$). Based on this, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant influence of staff training on educational planning strategies between federal and state universities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in educational planning strategies between staff with high and low exposure to training programmes in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Independent t-test Analysis of Difference Based on Training Exposure

Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
High Training Exposure	226	3.18	0.74	422	2.45	1.96	Reject H_0
Low Training Exposure	198	2.87	0.82				

The findings in Table 4 showed that staff with high exposure to training programmes had a mean score of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.74, whereas those with low exposure had a mean score of 2.87 and a standard deviation of 0.82. The independent t-test yielded a calculated t-value of 2.45, which exceeds the critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance ($df = 422$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in educational planning strategies based on staff exposure to training programmes.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The findings of this study reveal that staff training significantly influences educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State. The grand mean of 3.09 across all indicators of training's influence on planning represents a consistently high extent of impact. This finding aligns with the position of Ogunode, Kasimu and Sambo (2023), who argue that staff training in tertiary institutions enhances employees' technical, conceptual, and interpersonal competencies, which in turn improves their contributions to institutional development activities. Similarly, Omeni and Nkedishu (2021) found that teacher quality and efficiency output are fundamentally linked to how well academic staff are trained and retrained. The implication is that investment in staff training directly translates to improved planning

capabilities, which is consistent with the broader literature on human capital development (Kareem, 2019; Dessler, 2020).

Specifically, the finding that continuous professional development (CPD) has the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 3.21$) in influencing planning efficiency highlights the central importance of sustained, structured learning activities. This supports the argument of Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner (as cited in Fernandes et al, 2023) that effective professional development results in measurable changes in staff knowledge, practice, and institutional contributions. Universities in world-class settings, as noted by James et al., (2015), rely heavily on professional development centres to promote innovation and planning quality among academic staff. The finding that workshops and seminars improve planning outcomes ($\bar{x} = 2.98$) is also consistent with Manduna (2014) and Ogunode et al. (2021), who identified such structured learning activities as key drivers of staff capability development in the Nigerian tertiary education system.

The finding that academic staff with high training exposure demonstrate significantly better educational planning strategies than those with low exposure ($\bar{x} = 3.18$ vs. $\bar{x} = 2.87$) further corroborates earlier evidence from training studies in Africa. Samwel (2018) found in a Tanzanian university context that training significantly improves employee performance in academic institutions. In the Nigerian context, the study by Ugwu (2021) on career development and lecturer performance in South-East Nigeria also supports this finding, noting that systematic training and career development investment leads to more productive and strategy-oriented academic staff. The observed difference is also consistent with the human capital theory, which posits that investment in people through education and training yields returns in productivity and innovation (Salau et al., 2016).

The hypotheses testing confirmed that there is a significant difference in educational planning strategies between staff in federal and state universities ($t\text{-cal} = 2.11 > t\text{-crit} = 1.96$). This may be attributable to the disparate funding structures between federal and state universities in Nigeria, where federal universities tend to receive more TETFund interventions, research grants, and capacity-building resources, thereby enhancing their staff's planning competencies (TETFund, 2023; Oraegbunam, Obi, & Ohamobi, 2025). This finding resonates with Okonta and Nkedishu (2024), whose study highlighted systemic disparities in the distribution of educational resources and opportunities in Nigerian universities, including access to training and professional development programmes.

The second hypothesis testing also confirmed a significant difference between staff with high and low training exposure ($t\text{-cal} = 2.45 > t\text{-crit} = 1.96$). This implies that the frequency and depth of participation in training programmes meaningfully differentiates staff in terms of their capacity to engage in institutional planning. These findings are consistent with those of Chukwubueze (2022), whose study on administrative efficiencies and teachers' productivity in Delta State secondary schools found that staff who regularly participated in professional development were more efficient in their administrative roles. Nkedishu (2023) equally noted that the quality of strategies adopted by school administrators depends significantly on their exposure to professional development and security threat management training. Such studies collectively point to training exposure as a reliable predictor of planning quality and institutional contribution.

Furthermore, the findings are grounded in the broader literature on educational planning, which posits that effective institutional planning requires competent, knowledgeable, and regularly updated staff (Ololube, 2017; Ololube et al., 2016). Adebayo and Obinna (2020) similarly emphasised that capacity building and improved data management are essential for strengthening educational planning and policy execution in Nigeria. The present study adds to this body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence from Rivers State public universities, demonstrating that training is not merely a welfare provision but a strategic investment with measurable returns in planning quality.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of staff training on educational planning strategies in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings overwhelmingly indicate that staff training has a significant, positive influence on educational planning strategies. Academic staff who receive adequate

and regular training demonstrate superior planning capabilities, contribute more effectively to institutional decision-making, and engage more productively in policy implementation processes. Conversely, limited training exposure is associated with weaker planning performance, highlighting the critical importance of sustained investment in professional development for university academic staff.

The study also established a statistically significant difference in educational planning strategies between staff in federal and state universities, as well as between those with high and low training exposure. These differences suggest that structural and resource disparities among institutions, as well as individual differences in training engagement, have tangible consequences for the quality of educational planning. In light of these findings, it is concluded that staff training is a non-negotiable element of effective educational planning in Rivers State public universities and, by extension, across the Nigerian university system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University management and relevant government agencies should strengthen and sustain structured staff training programmes, including workshops, seminars, and conferences, with a specific focus on building competencies in institutional planning, policy formulation, and strategic decision-making.
2. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and State Ministry of Education should expand their capacity building interventions to cover state universities and ensure equity in access to training resources between federal and state university staff, thereby reducing planning disparities.
3. A mandatory annual professional development requirement should be institutionalised for all academic staff, particularly in areas of educational management, planning techniques, and policy implementation, to ensure that all staff maintain high levels of planning competence.
4. University management should develop internal training calendars that align with institutional planning cycles, ensuring that staff training is strategically timed to prepare academic staff adequately before major planning exercises.

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